

Multi-Depth Soil Moisture Monitoring Within A Single And Dual Axis Tracking Agrivoltaic System In Brandenburg, North-Eastern Germany

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1. Introduction

Microclimate, rainfall distribution, and solar radiation are influenced by Agrivoltaic (AV) systems which, in turn, affect soil water dynamics. Soil moisture is a critical parameter for crops in sandy soils, as low levels can lead to drought stress, triggering adaptations such as reduced shoot growth, accelerated fruit ripening, the formation of smaller seeds, or premature leaf and fruit drop [1]. Underneath AV systems, higher soil moisture levels can occur compared to reference plots, particularly in dryland regions with annual precipitation below 300 mm [2]. Additionally, spatial heterogeneity in soil moisture may arise due to the uneven shading from solar modules [3] or rainfall interception, wind direction, and tilting angles of the solar panels [4]. Understanding these dynamics is essential because soil moisture directly impacts crop growth and yield. Therefore, we aim to analyse the spatial-temporal dynamics of soil moisture across multiple depths and identify the drivers of their variability.

Although there has been considerable research on AV, clear strategies for sensor placement and the integration of measured data into optimization frameworks to enhance synergies between the AV system and the cropping system remain lacking. Therefore, with the newly installed sensor system, we aim to analyse the data and use it as input for models to optimize the management of both the crop and the AV system. While the project is still in its early stages, this presentation will focus on the design and implementation of the monitoring infrastructure, preliminary observations, and the development of a data management strategy to handle and analyse large, multi-dimensional datasets. By sharing our methodology and initial outcomes, we aim to contribute to best practices in monitoring and data management for AV systems.

2. Methods

Our study explores the integration of an advanced multi-parameter soil monitoring systems in profiles and transects within a 2024 newly built 4 m high-elevated, single- and dual axis tracking AV installation with a capacity of 580 kWp, 832 solar panels (Fig. 1 - left). The AV rows are orientated with a direction of approx. 140° (northwest to southeast). The spacing between the steel profiles of different rows is 10 m for the single axis and 16 m for the dual axis tracking AV system. The installation incorporates 75 soil sensors (model WET150, Delta-T Devices, United Kingdom) at 25 locations with depths of 45 cm, 75 cm, and 95 cm to capture spatial-temporal changes in moisture content, temperature, and electrical conductivity. The

data from the AV system will be compared with a reference plot located in close spatial proximity with a comparable soil moisture monitoring set-up. The study site with sandy soils is located on a field (0.7 ha) at the research station of the Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF) in the city of Müncheberg (52.52° latitude, 14.12° longitude, and 63 m above sea level) in Brandenburg, 50 km east of Berlin. The long-term (1991–2020) average annual temperature at this site is 9.6°C, with an average annual precipitation of 552 mm [5].

Fig. 1: Images of the single axis tracking AV system and installation of multi-parameter soil monitoring systems. Left) UAV image of the AV system - visible here are the four trenches (from the left to right) needed for the installation of the cable ducts and soil-sensors. Right) Detailed view of one trench in the middle row under the AV. (photos: M. Donat, ZALF).

3. Outlook

The aim of the project is to enhance energy and crop yields through an optimization framework. The data from the soil monitoring system will be linked with real-time AV tracking positions, energy production, weather and microclimate data, as well as plant health and growth status and will be used as an input for shadow simulations, crop and economic modeling for monitoring and decision support. This setup will enable us to evaluate the impact of varying light regimes and shading patterns on soil conditions over time, providing valuable insights for optimizing crop management under AV systems.

4. References

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